

The effect of premarital classes on the level of knowledge of reproductive health and participation in premarital check up on prospective bride and groom

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Abstract

Introduction: The bride and groom are who are about to get married may still not realize how important premarital check-ups are. Even though this examination is very helpful in identifying health problems and risks for yourself and your partner. Seeing this fact, the provision of sexual and reproductive health education needs to be given to prospective bride and groom who will enter the marriage gate.

Objective: This research was to determine the effect of premarital classes on the level of reproductive health knowledge and premarital check up participation in prospective brides and grooms.

Method: This type of research is observational quantitative research with a cross-sectional approach. Sampling using consecutive sampling method. Respondents were 110 bride and groom who attended premarital classes at PUSPAGA Surabaya City in September 2024. Data collection using an instrument in the form of a questionnaire filled in by the bride and groom.

Result: From the results of the analysis, it was found that almost all prospective bride and groom had good knowledge and all prospective brides were willing to take premarital check-ups after attending premarital classes. The results of statistical tests using the Wilcoxon test obtained a p-value = 0.00 (p value <0.05). There is an effect of premarital classes on the level of reproductive health knowledge and participation in premarital check-ups in prospective bride and groom.

Conclusion: There is an effect of premarital classes on the level of reproductive health knowledge and participation in premarital check-ups in prospective bride and groom.

Keywords: Premarital Classes; Knowledge; Reproduction Health; Premarital Check Up; Bride and Groom

1 Introduction

The bride and groom are the beginning of a family, therefore, it is important for bride and groom to prepare their health conditions in order to carry out a healthy pregnancy so that they can give birth to a healthy next generation and create a healthy, prosperous and quality family [1]. Every prospective bride and groom must know about the health of themselves and their partners, including reproductive health, conditions/diseases that can interfere with reproductive health, such as anemia, malnutrition, sexually transmitted infections including Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immuno Deficiency (AIDS), other infectious diseases, non-communicable diseases and genetic diseases,

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as well as contraceptive services [2]. Knowledge about reproductive health can encourage couples to openly discuss sexual elements in marriage and motivate jointly issues about partner expectations from sexual relations in marriage.

According to the health profile of East Java Province in 2022 the number of prospective bride and groom in East Java was 512,247. However, only 355,973 took a premarital health test or premarital check up or about 69.5% of prospective bride and groom. Premarital check up is a health check conducted by bride and groom before marriage towards healthy and planned pregnancy preparation. Premarital check up or premarital screening is important to avoid problems of pain, spiritual and physical disability, death, and towards achieving the health and well-being of mothers and newborns (well born baby and well health mother).

Bride and groom who are about to get married may still not realize how important premarital check-ups are. In fact, this examination is very helpful in identifying health problems and risks for yourself and your partner. Seeing this fact, the provision of sexual and reproductive health education needs to be given to prospective brides who will enter the marriage gate. Through the provision of this health education, it is hoped that bride and groom can prepare themselves for family life including planning a healthy pregnancy so that they can give birth to a quality next generation. Not only women who will become prospective mothers who need to do premarital check-ups, but also men need to do this, preferably coming together with a partner when doing this examination [3].

Research on the effect of premarital classes on the level of reproductive health knowledge and participation in premarital check-ups on prospective bride and groom is quite rare because some studies only examine the relationship between the characteristics of prospective bride-to-be and the level of knowledge instead of knowing the effect or effectiveness of premarital classes. Therefore, researchers want to conduct further research related to the effect of premarital classes on the level of reproductive health knowledge and participation in premarital check-ups in prospective brides and grooms.

2 Material and methods

This type of research is observational quantitative research with a cross sectional approach. Sampling using consecutive sampling method. Respondents were 110 brides-to-be who attended premarital classes at PUSPAGA Surabaya City in September 2024. Data collection using an instrument in the form of a questionnaire filled in by the bride and groom. The collected data were recorded for entry and processed using Microsoft excel and SPSS.

3 Results and Discussion

The research data and its analysis are presented in the form of tables and narratives. The purpose is to find out information about data on gender, age, education, occupation, level of reproductive health knowledge of prospective brides before and after attending premarital classes, and participation in premarital check-ups of prospective brides before and after attending premarital classes.

The results of this study are known to show the frequency distribution of prospective brides based on the gender category, most of the prospective brides are male as many as 57 people (51.8%) but only a small difference with prospective brides as many as 53 people (48.2%). The frequency distribution based on the age category, most of the prospective brides in the range of 20-35 years as many as 78 people (70.9%). Frequency distribution based on the last education history, almost all prospective brides have the last education in the middle category, both high school and vocational school, as many as 81 people (73.6%). The frequency distribution of bride and groom based on occupation is half of the bride and groom work in the private sector as many as 55 people (50%).

Tabel 1 Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of Respondents	Frequency (f)N=110	Presentation%
Gender		
Male	57	51.8
Female	53	48.2
Age		
<20	2	1.8

20-35	78	70.9
>35	30	27.3
Education		
Elementary	12	10.9
Secondary School	81	73.6
Higher	17	15.5
Occupation		
CIVIL SERVANT	8	7.3
Self-employed	16	14.5
Private	55	50
Not Working	28	25.5
Other	3	2.7

Tabel 2 Reproductive Health Knowledge Level of Prospective Brides Before and After Attending Premarital Classes

Knowledge Category	Before Premarital Classes		After Premarital Classes	
	N	%	N	%
Good	66	60	92	83.6
Fair	42	38.2	13	11.8
Less	2	1.8	5	4.5
Total	110	100	110	100

The results showed that there were changes in the level of knowledge of prospective brides related to reproductive health before and after attending premarital classes. There was an increase in the knowledge of prospective brides who had good knowledge, which initially before attending premarital classes was only 66 people (60%) to 92 people (83.6%) after attending premarital classes.

Tabel 3 Premarital Check Up Participation of Prospective Brides Before and After Participating in Premarital Classes

Participation Category	Before Premarital Classes		After Premarital Classes	
	N	%	N	%
Willing	59	53.6	110	100
Not Willing	51	46.4	0	0
Total	110	100	110	100

The results showed that before attending premarital classes, 46.4% of prospective brides had an unwilling attitude, after attending premarital classes there was a decrease to 0%, which meant that all prospective brides were willing to take part in premarital check-ups. Meanwhile, before attending premarital classes, 53.6% of respondents had a willing attitude and increased to 100% after attending premarital classes.

Table 4 The Effect of Premarital Classes on the Level of Knowledge of Reproductive Health of Prospective Brides and Grooms

Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max	P-value
Before Premarital Classes	110	7.93	8.0	1.16	4	10	0.000
After Premarital Classes	110	8.96	10	1.68	2	10	

The statistical test results using the Wilcoxon signed rank-test test obtained a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05). By setting a significant degree of $\alpha = 0.05$, H_1 is accepted because the p-value $\leq \alpha$. Based on these results, it can be concluded that premarital classes have an influence on the level of knowledge of prospective brides related to reproductive health.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Sepsiana (2020) regarding health education related to reproductive health in prospective brides. The results of the analysis showed a value of $p = 0.000$ or $p < 0.05$, this proves that health education such as premarital classes affects the level of reproductive health knowledge of prospective brides [4]. This is also reinforced by research conducted by Zulaizeh (2023) regarding the effect of health education on increasing the knowledge of prospective brides about premarital health. From the results of the analysis it is known that there are differences before and after being given health education as evidenced by the Wilcoxon test analysis with a p-value of 0.000 or $p < 0.05$ [5].

Increased knowledge is related to a learning process, one of which is health education. Through premarital classes, prospective brides will get health education which will have an impact on increasing the level of knowledge [6]. Through the provision of health education treatment, it also has an impact on increasing one's level of proficiency in an object. By providing health education, brides-to-be understand the importance of reproductive health before and after marriage [7].

Table 5 The Effect of Premarital Classes on the Participation of Premarital Check Up Prospective Brides

Group	N	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max	P-value
Before Premarital Classes	110	0.54	1	0.50	0	1	0.000
After Premarital Classes	110	1	1	0	1	1	

The statistical test results using the Wilcoxon signed rank-test test obtained a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05). By setting a significant degree $\alpha = 0.05$, H_1 is accepted because the p-value $\leq \alpha$. Based on these results, it can be concluded that premarital classes have an influence on the participation of prospective brides in premarital check-ups.

This study is in line with research conducted by Puspita Sari and Ernawati (2023) on reproductive health education of prospective brides on knowledge and participation in premarital check-ups, which says that there is an effect of education on reproductive health of prospective brides before and after being given an intervention on the participation of premarital check-ups as evidenced by the McNemar test with a p value of 0.016 (<0.05) [8]. This research is also supported by research conducted by Susanti (2018) regarding the effect of premarital health education on the knowledge and attitudes of prospective brides in Lubuk Begalung Padang in 2017, which states that there is an effect of premarital health education on the attitude of prospective brides in Lubuk Begalung District, Padang City and proven by a p value of 0.035 (<0.05) [9].

Participation in this case is the attitude of the bride-to-be towards premarital check up. Attitude is a response to a situation or condition that results in a decision whether or not to do something based on understanding, perception, and feelings. Attitude is a form of response that causes action towards an object, whether it is negative or positive [9]. This is in line with L. green's theory which says that a person's health behavior is influenced by knowledge as a predisposition to determine real action or behavior, which means that the existence of understanding in a person will form a sense of confidence which ultimately provides a basis for making a decision [10]. Therefore, brides-to-be who have attended premarital classes will change their mindset to participate in premarital check-ups. Brides-to-be who have attended premarital classes will gain an understanding of the importance of reproductive health so that they will be more aware of their health conditions and are willing to take part in premarital check-ups as a first step to forming a healthy family [11].

4 Conclusion

From the research that has been done, it can be concluded that before attending premarital classes most of the bride and groom are well informed, but after attending premarital classes the number increases so that almost all brides and grooms are well informed and before attending premarital classes only half of the number of brides and grooms are willing to take part in premarital check-ups, but after attending premarital classes all brides and grooms are willing to take part in premarital check-ups. From this statement, it can be concluded that there is an effect of premarital classes on the level of reproductive health knowledge and participation in premarital check-ups in prospective brides.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure Conflict of interest

The author declared no potential conflicts of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

This study was approved by the ethics committee of health research of the faculty of medicine, airlangga university (116/EC/KEPK/FKUA/2024).

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